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supply to the crop throughout the growth period.

These observations confirm that the use of CRU 6% fertilizer and the chlorophyll meter technique (SPAD-N) produces high grain yields with high N uptake and efficiency. CRU 6% also appeared to be better than CRU 4.5%, probably due to its slower N release profile. If CRU could be priced competitively with the commonly available PU, it could become the preferred N fertilizer for rice.

Real-time N management using the chlorophyll meter and PU represents an attractive alternative for improving grain yields and N use efficiency in rice.

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Assessment of chlorophyll meter-based N application at critical growth stages of irrigated transplanted rice

S.P. Ramanathan and R. Nagarajan, SWMRI, Thanjavur, India; and V. Balasubramanian, IRRI

Synchronizing nitrogen (N) application with crop demand and soil N supply is one strategy for improving N use efficiency (NUE) in rice. Using a variable N rate application based on observed chlorophyll meter readings at critical growth stages may help optimize grain yield and NUE at the same time. The chlorophyll or SPAD meter can accurately measure leaf chlorophyll content that is related to leaf N status. It could help develop need-based N fertilization in rice (Peng et al 1996). One disadvantage of the SPAD technique, however, is the need for weekly observations to monitor crop N status, which could sometimes lead to many (3–6) split N applications (Balasubramanian et al 1999).

Field experiments were conducted during the 1997-98 dry (DS, kuruvai: June to September) and wet (WS-II, thaladi: October to February) seasons at the SWMRI farm in Thanjavur, India. The objective was to determine whether chlorophyll meter readings taken only at critical crop growth stages—early tillering, active tillering, panicle initiation, and 10% flowering—were sufficient, and to apply variable rates of N based on a range of SPAD threshold values (Table 1) rather than on a single critical SPAD value. The effect of variable rate N application, based on a range of chlorophyll meter readings, on

grain yield and NUE was measured in these trials. Treatments included different ranges of SPAD threshold values: <32, 33–35, and 36–38. Rice varieties ADT42 (115 d) and ADT38 (135 d) were used during the DS and WS-II, respectively. Treatments were arranged in a completely randomized block design with seven replications.

SPAD readings were taken in all treatments at critical crop growth stages using the youngest fully expanded leaf of 10 randomly selected plants from each plot. Whenever average SPAD readings fell within a set range of threshold values, N was applied immediately based on the variable rates specified in Table 1. Plant N status was allowed to fall to the specific range of SPAD values for each treatment before N was applied.

Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) was determined at 14% moisture content from three 5-m² sample areas taken from each plot. The NUE

is expressed as the partial factor productivity of applied N (PFP-N).

Grain yields were low in both the 1997-98 DS and WS due to heavy flooding at critical crop growth stages. Among the SPAD threshold ranges used in the DS, the 36–38 range gave the highest grain yield (4.9 t ha⁻¹), but it was not significantly different from that of SPAD <32 (4.7 t ha⁻¹) or 33–35 (4.6 t ha⁻¹) (Table 2). The NUE as expressed by the PFP-N value was 125 for SPAD <32, 92 for SPAD 33–36, and 54 for SPAD 36–38. The data seem to indicate that a SPAD threshold range of 36–38 could be optimum for DS rice crops. Further research is ongoing to confirm these results.

In the WS, the highest grain yield was obtained from SPAD 36–38; this was not significantly different from that of SPAD 33–35, but significantly different from that of SPAD <32 (Table 2). More N

Table 1. Amount of N applied (kg ha⁻¹) based on range of SPAD threshold values observed at critical crop growth stages.

Range of SPAD threshold values	Early tillering (14 DAT)*	Active tillering (28 DAT)	Panicle initiation (42 DAT)	Flowering (56 DAT)
<32	30	50	50	30
33–35	30	40	40	30
36–38	20	30	30	20

*DAT = d after transplanting.

Table 2. Effect of variable rate N application based on range of SPAD values observed at critical crop growth stages on yield and N use efficiency of irrigated transplanted rice at the SWMRI farm, Thanjavur, India, 1997-98 dry (DS) and wet seasons (WS).^a

Range of SPAD threshold values	Total N applied (kg ha ⁻¹)		Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		PFP-N ^b	
	DS	WS	DS	WS	DS	WS
<32	38	58	4.7 a	3.3 b	125	57
33-35	50	70	4.6 a	3.7 ab	92	53
36-38	92	104	4.9 a	4.0 a	54	38
SE ^c			347		202	
LSD ^c (5%)			ns ^c		530	

^aP, K, and Zn were applied to all treatments at the rate of 22-42-10 kg ha⁻¹ in the DS and 26-50-10 kg ha⁻¹ in the WS. ^bPFP-N = total grain yield per kilogram N applied. ^cns = not significant. ^eSE = standard error; LSD = least significant difference.

(104 kg ha⁻¹), however, was required at this range to produce a yield of 4.0 t ha⁻¹, which resulted in a low PFP-N value of 38. SPAD <32 produced the lowest yield with a to-

tal N use of 58 kg ha⁻¹ (PFP-N = 57). Waiting for SPAD values to fall below 32 before applying N fertilizer may have starved plants for N during the long intervals be-

tween N topdressing in this treatment. These observations suggested that, for grain yield and NUE, a SPAD threshold range of 33-35 could be optimum for the WS rice in the new Cauvery Delta zone.

References

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Chlorophyll meter threshold values for N management in wet direct-seeded irrigated rice

V. Balasubramanian and A.C. Morales, IRRI; and R.T. Cruz, Philippine Rice Research Institute (PhilRice), Maligaya, Nueva Ecija, Philippines

Asian rice farmers are increasingly adopting wet seeding as an alternative method to transplanting for economic and technical reasons. High-density, excessive early vegetative growth and low foliar N concentration (Schnier et al 1990, Peng et al 1996b) characterize wet direct-seeded rice (W-DSR). These characteristics will have an impact on the critical leaf N concentration required for high grain yields in W-DSR.

The chlorophyll or SPAD meter offers a new strategy for synchronizing N application with actual crop demand in rice (Peng et al 1996a, Balasubramanian et al 1999). Earlier studies indicated that the SPAD threshold or critical value of 35 established for transplanted rice invariably overestimated the N requirement of and reduced the N use efficiency (NUE) in W-DSR (IRRI-CREMNET 1996). This study was undertaken to establish specific SPAD threshold values for maximizing both grain yield and NUE in W-DSR in the Philippines.

In collaboration with PhilRice, we conducted on-farm trials at Maligaya in the

1996 dry (DS) and wet seasons (WS) and in the 1997 DS (DS: December/January-April; WS: July-October). The objective was to compare the grain yield and NUE of irrigated W-DSR under different N management practices. In the 1996 trials, the SPAD method with a single SPAD threshold of 35 was compared with the farmers' practice and a zero-N control. The farmers' practice consisted of 150 kg ha⁻¹ N application in two or three splits in the DS and 90 kg N ha⁻¹ in the WS. In the 1997 DS, different SPAD threshold levels (29, 32, and 35) were evaluated along with a fixed N application rate of 120 kg ha⁻¹ in two or three splits and a zero-N control. Treatments were arranged in a randomized complete block design with each farm as a replication. The mean amount of P and K applied was 13 kg P ha⁻¹ and 25 kg K ha⁻¹ in the 1996 DS, 17 kg P ha⁻¹ and 28 kg K ha⁻¹ in the 1996 WS, and 26 kg P ha⁻¹ and 50 kg K ha⁻¹ in the 1997 DS.

SPAD readings were taken in all treatments weekly starting from 21 d after

seeding (DAS) until first flowering, using the youngest fully expanded leaf of 10 randomly selected plants from each plot. For the SPAD-N treatments, N was applied whenever the mean SPAD reading fell below the chosen threshold values. The N rates applied were 30, 45, and 30 kg ha⁻¹ in the DS and 20, 30, and 20 kg ha⁻¹ in the WS during the early (21-35 DAS), rapid (36-56 DAS), and late (57 DAS-flowering) growth stages, respectively. The P and K rates applied followed the local farmers' practice.

Grain yield was expressed in kg ha⁻¹ at 14% moisture content. Two indicators of N use efficiency were used in this study: agronomic efficiency of applied N (AEN) and partial factor productivity of N (PFP-N).

In the 1996 DS, grain yields and efficiency values (AEN and PFP-N) were high for 3-N splits in broadcast and 2-N splits in row-seeded rice (Table 1). In spite of the high yields, SPAD-35 N was the least efficient due to a high N rate of 213 kg